

Analysis of Personality Traits' and General Attitudes' Differences Among Age Groups and Possible Business Economics Implications

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Abstract - Many types of research of generations and age groups' characteristics emphasize the differences and specifics. This paper emphasizes relatively permanent psychological constructs: personality traits (according to Jung's typology) and general attitudes (according to Spranger's classification), focusing on age groups. Individuals born in period 1996 - 2000 reached adulthood and started making decisions on their own; they have become (or will soon become) part of the labor force, thus increasing their purchasing power, and their share in population (and market) will increase in the years to come. This research aims to determine the differences in personality traits and general attitudes expression concerning the age groups, focusing on the last age group. A convenience sample of 331 respondents has been collected for this research. A nonparametric one-way analysis of variance is applied to transversal data to determine if personality traits and general attitudes expressions show statistically significant differences between the three age groups. The results show no statistically significant differences in personality traits expression given the respondents' belonging to three age groups, while statistically significant difference occurs for individualistic, aesthetical, and social general attitudes. Results' implications are relevant for theoretical and practical application in employee analysis in the fields of human resources management and internal marketing, as well as for negotiation and purchase behavior analysis in marketing science. Given the established similarities between the age groups, a derived recommendation emphasizes similarities while overcoming age groups' differences.

Keywords: personality traits, general attitudes, analysis of variance

I. INTRODUCTION

Society is exposed to constant changes. Those changes were less expressed in history, but speeding up in technological, economic, and scientific development causes more frequent changes in individual's environments while growing up, resulting in differences among individuals of different age cohorts. Most research on characteristics of specific age cohorts and generations emphasize the generation gap, differences, and novelties, while similarities mostly remain ignored and unexplored. Besides that, the questioning of whether the differences arise from the changes in environmental or internal individual features is rarely investigated. The emphasis of this research is set on individual psychological features, or precisely, personality traits and general attitudes. Personality represents a relatively permanent and stable combination of an individual's characteristics and creates a unique behavioral pattern, which denotes an individual's adjustment to the

environment, and enables anticipation of the individual's behavior up to a certain extent. General attitudes describe a pattern in individuals' reactions to their environment, whereby attitudes' hierarchy and intensity are precisely defined. Both personality traits and general attitudes are frequently used in economics while assessing and predicting individuals' behavior. Stated psychological traits represent relatively permanent constructs, and the relevance of their analysis follows from the permanent characteristics – specifically, long-term determinants of an individual's behavior. The analysis will explore the question of significant differences in traits and personality types over the age groups and differences in general attitudes. The analysis is based on a convenience sample from Croatia.

The rest of the paper offers an overview of classification and specifics of age groups, personality traits, and general attitudes; section Methods describes data collection and analysis; section Results offers an overview of conclusions based on analysis; section Discussion and conclusion points out theoretical and practical implications of the results.

II. GENERATIONS AND AGE GROUPS

According to Underwood (2007:43), the generation denotes an age group that shares unique experiences and learning through the formative years, thus creating a unique set of basic values and attitudes that differs one generation from others. Williams and Page (2010) divide generations according to the birth-year to pre-depression (before 1930), depression (1930 – 1945), baby boom generation (1945 – 1964), generation X (1965 – 1976), generation Y (1977 – 1994) and generation Z (after 1994). There are disparities in determining birth-age for generation Y (also known as millennials) and generation Z among the subject researchers. Twenge (2017) names the later iGen. Ozkan and Solmaz (2015) define generation Z as persons born after 2000, while persons born in the period from 1980 to 2000 belong to generation Y or the Millennials. Bencsik, Horváth-Csikós, and Juhász (2016) determine generation Z by the birth-years from 1995 – 2010 and name the following generation (individuals born after 2010) the alpha-generation. According to DelCampo, Haggerty, Knippel, and Haneyu (2011), persons born between 1981 and 2000 belong to generation Y. Laurel (2005) determines generation Y by the years of birth from 1980 to 2000. According to Tulgan (2013), everyone born between 1978 and 2000 belong to one big, millennial generation. Wells, Fishman, Horton, and Rowe

(2018), find that individuals that turned between 18 and 22 years in 2018 create generation Z. Overview of the generations' division by the year of birth shows overlaps for persons born between 1994 and 2000.

Even though birth years represent only reference limits for a particular generation, as this research deals with age groups and not generations, a specific frame needs to be chosen. A framework for the last generation suggested by Wells et al. (2018) will be used for this research.

In order to investigate psychological differences in the generational perspective, longitudinal research is required. This research will examine differences between age groups of respondents based on cross-sectional data, and age groups will be defined according to the generational division. The research emphasis is set on respondents from the last age group, as these individuals are nearing the end of their formative years and will start (or already have started) making their economic impact. To present a comprehensive insight into the characteristics of members of the youngest age group, an overview of existing research is presented in continuation.

Numerous observations about generations Y and Z are focused on differences in thinking and learning. Postolov, Magdinceva Sopova, and Janeska Iliev (2017) emphasize the influence of new technologies on learning, focusing on e-learning. Karakas et al. (2015) distinguish three main difficulties in learning for new generations: the lack of concentration, the lack of engagement, and the lack of social life.

Ilišin and Gvozdanović (2016) analyze the structure and dynamics of youth values in Croatia, given respondents' social environment, situations, and personal interests. Using comparative analysis, they determined that the scale of individual and social values in youth remained stable over 30 years, with values in the private sphere on the top of the scale and values in the public sphere on the bottom. In addition, they point out that the newest generation of youth demonstrates a smaller intensity of tested values. The same research offers a comparison of the results from the years 1986 and 2013, which derived authors' conclusion that youth's valuation of leisure, professional success, and political confirmation has diminished, with an increase in valuation of religion, nationality, government, and autonomy.

Age groups also represent the demographic characteristic of individuals and are frequently used in market segmentation. Many kinds of research in that fields focus on behavior analysis in purchase situations, decision making and labor market behavior of members of particular age group and generation (DelCampo et al. 2011, Bencsik et al., 2016, Ozkan and Solmaz, 2015, Williams and Page, 2011, Underwood, 2007, Karakas, Manisaligil and Sarigollu, 2015, Pomarici and Vecchio 2014, Razum, Pandža Bajs, and Zekić, 2017, Krasulja, Radojević, Janjušić and Vujić, 2015). A part of the stated research is directed toward the analysis of previous generations. The interest for the members of the youngest age group increases as its members approach the majority, and Priporas, Stylos, and Fotiadis (2017) explore the perception, expectations, and recommendations for the development of smart retail and find the relevance in employing electronic

processes in retail while ensuring speed and autonomy in a purchase. Ozkan and Solmaz (2015b) examine the generation Z members' relation toward the work. The results of respondents self-assessments show that respondents find themselves to trust themselves (97.5%), be loyal (96.7%), be hardworking (96.7%), agree with anyone able to (80%), be loved by everyone (92.4%), honest (96%), conciliatory (87.6%), helpful (79%), unrealistic/ dreamers (75.9%), open to working in the group (88.4%), innovative (86.7%). Authors offer a comparison to the previous generation, pointing out similarities. Both generations like to use technology while achieving their goals, members of both generations like to participate in projects, and prefer to work in the offices (second reported choice for the place of the work is co-working space). The difference arises from the generation Z members' more intensive need that superiors listen to their ideas and value their opinion, while generation Y members show a more intensive need that superiors allow autonomy in work. Krasulja et al. (2015) systematize specific characteristics of generations and find the following set of characteristics relevant for members of generation Z: networked; raised in the "culture of fear" and mobile technologies, with "helicopter" parenting and social media; expecting communication whenever and wherever they want; facing problems of lost identity; the lack of employment possibilities; and unfulfilled expectations. The flaws of the members of generation Z present overconfidence in their knowledge and expectation of prompt results. Wells et al. (2018) denote trends related to generation Z: generation Z is in many perspectives more similar to generation X than to generation Y; they declare to be spiritual, but not religious; they declare to be members of middle socioeconomic status despite the increase in the difference between lower and higher socioeconomic status (which will lead to the rise of the political center, according to the authors); seek purpose (which lead to emphasizing purpose in advertising messages and companies missions that target them as consumers).

However, stated conclusions have to be treated with caution, as members of the last age group just stepped into the labor market, and their work-related attitudes, relations to work, and consumption behavior yet have to mature. Besides, it is hard to determine a simple age limit when an individual becomes an adult, and the overview by Knežević (2018) points out that some concepts emphasize 18th year as the age limit, while others reach the early twenties; even legally defined majority is not equally defined among countries. A part of the research about members of the generation Z was conducted during their adolescence, and the changes individuals go through in that period can vastly influence behavior, general and specific attitudes, and character traits. The specifics of the last age group are eagerly expected, primarily because of their applications in business and economics. However, all of the conclusions remain to be reexamined and confirmed once the members reach adulthood.

A. *General attitudes*

Socialization represents a formal and informal transfer of culture, tradition, attitudes, beliefs, norms, and social rules to

the individual. The listed factors become an integral part of the general values and attitudes with the process of internalization. Hanisch et al. (1998) determine scientific relevance of the general attitudes in individual repeated behaviors, and authors Chen, Goodard and Casper (2004), Bye et al. (2011), Parks and Guay (2012), Tagiuri (1989), Young (1992) and Kaže (2010a, 2010b), point out to connection between general attitudes and consumer behavior and labor market behavior.

The most commonly used universal division of general attitudes was created by Spranger (1928). Rokeach's (1973) and Schwartz's (1992) general attitudes divisions are also

frequently used. Given the number of the observed variables, the fact that Rokeach's division has elements already present in personality traits, and the dimension that emphasis determining differences between cultures, Spranger division's simplicity represents the optimal choice for this research. According to that division, general attitudes are derived by scaling general values. Spranger divides general attitudes as individualistic (I), theoretical (T), traditional (Tr), social (S), economic (E), and aesthetical (A) general attitude (Table I offers a systematization according to Spranger (1928) and Klassen et al. (2009)).

TABLE I
THE OVERVIEW OF DESCRIPTION AND INDICATORS OF GENERAL ATTITUDES

General attitude	The description of values and characteristics related to the general attitude	Terms/ indicators of general attitude
Theoretical general attitude (T)	pursuit of the truth; gaining the new information; revealing regularities; eagerness for gaining, evaluation and systematization of the knowledge; aspiration to understanding; tendency to empirics, evidence-base, critical thinking and rationality	Rationality, objectivity, learning, problem solving, intellectual strength, analyzing, clarity, importance of the knowledge
Individualistic general attitude (I)	gaining power, influence, competitiveness; aspiration for status and prestige; tendency to control; tendency to stand out, be unique and special	Power, control, influence, competitiveness, managing, independence, status, respect, responsibility
Social general attitude (S)	love for people; care for others; altruism and empathy; aspiration to general well-being and emphasis on interpersonal relationships	orientation to others, support, help, action to improve society, generosity, selflessness, compassion
Aesthetical general attitude (A)	striving for harmony, form, beauty, pleasure and fun; aspiration to achieve balance; enjoying the moment and subjective understanding of the experience	expressiveness, harmony, predominance of the form over the essence, balance, tolerance, creativity, self-fulfillment, beauty, subjectivity
Economic general attitude (E)	decision-making based on profits and benefits; estimates the investment of the effort, time and resources with respect to the expected profit; evaluation of the environment and self, based on economic and material indicators; striving for practical solutions and applications	practicality, financial interests, efficiency, usefulness, productivity, profit maximization, results
Traditional general attitude (Tr)	respect for rules, hierarchy, established forms; aspiration to unity, generally accepted ways and values; striving to establish order, structure and routines; respect for the system;	systematics, routines, rows, tradition, structure, focused, rules, principles

Source: adjusted from Kostelić (2017), systematization according to Spranger (1928) and Klassen et al. (2009).

B. Personality traits

Besides the general attitudes, personality traits also represent relatively permanent psychological constructs. The most commonly used models are the five-factor model (also known as the Big Five model) and Jung's (1929) personality typology. The first model is more frequently used to assess the psychiatric population because it contains the neuroticism trait.

Jung's typology of personalities is the framework that was a base for the later developed model by Keirsey and Bates (1984) and Myers - Briggs Type Indication (abbreviation: MBTI; Myers, McCaulley, Quenk and Hammer, 1998). Furnham

(2006) examines and compares stated typologies and finds a significant correlation between the four traits of the five-factor model and Myers – Briggs model. The only uncorrelated trait is the neuroticism trait, which appears only in the five-factor model.

Jung's personality typology was further developed by Myers and Briggs, and Keirsey and Bates. It consists of four personality traits, and each of them has opposite poles and consists of positive and negative characteristics. The combination of poles of the personality traits creates sixteen personality types. Table II offers systematization of the personality traits according to Jung (1971) and Myers et al. (1998).

TABLE II
OVERVIEW OF CHARACTERISTICS FOR EACH PERSONALITY TRAIT POLE

Extraversion (E)	Introversion (I)
Initiators	Reserved, do not stand out, waiting for others to approach them
Expressive	Retained, controlled, hard to get-to-know, prefer privacy
Social	Intimacy, they strive for a more intimate approach, prefer individual conversations, are linked to others at individual level
social, immediate, initiate acquaintance	
demonstrative, easy to get to know, reveal information about themselves	
seek popularity, have a wide circle of friends, are included in the groups	

Active Enthusiastic Sensing	interactive, seeking contact, listening and speaking lively, energetic, in the center of attention (S)	Reflective Quiet Intuitive	observers, seek space for themselves, read and write calm, enjoying solitude, seek support (N)
Specific	concrete facts, prefer literal, tangible	Abstract	they imagine, prefer symbols and intangible
Realistic	conscientious, emphasize the essence, strive to effectiveness	Imaginative	resourceful, inventive, looking for novelties
Practical	pragmatic, oriented to the outcome, applicability	Conceptual	scholars, oriented to ideas, intellectual
Experimenters	experience world with hands, empirical, trust experience	Theorists	seek samples, hypotheses, believe in theories
Traditional	conventional, love customs, tried and tested ways	Original	unconventional, different, new and unusual
Thinking	(T)	Feeling	(F)
Logical	non-personal, seeking impartiality, objective analysis	Empathetic	personal, seek understanding, emphasize the basic values
Reasonable	truthfulness, defining causes and consequences, respect for principles	Compassionate	tactical, sympathetic, loyal
Questioning	precision, challenges, seek debate	Approving	approve, agree, desire harmony
Critics	skeptical, looking for evidence, critical	Receptive	tolerant, believe, praise
Demanding	firm, sharp, goal-oriented	Gentle	gentle, gentle-hearted, meaning-oriented
Judging	(J)	Perceiving	(P)
Systematic	neat, structured, do not like diversion	Informal	relaxed, comfy, disruptions are welcome
Planning	future-oriented, plan ahead, create solid plans	Open	oriented to the present, make flexible plans, follow the development of the situation
Early starters	motivated by self-discipline, steady progress, delay causes stress	Pressure boosted	motivated by pressure, work spurts and at times, an early start discourages them
Scheduled	seek routines, create lists, procedures to help them	Spontaneous	seek variety, enjoy surprises, hinder the procedures
Methodical	plan specific activities, write sub-tasks, organized	Emerging	leap in the unknown, allow the strategies to appear on the go, adaptable

Source: adjusted from Kostelić (2017), systematization by Jung (1971) and Myers et al. (1998).

Personality traits, as psychological variables, are derived from the answers to a questionnaire. The questionnaire is formed to enable the connection of the answers to a certain pole of the trait.

The combination of personality traits creates personality types. There are sixteen personality types given the traits' number and poles (Myers et al., 1998). It is common to replace the trait poles with abbreviations: extraversion (E), introversion (I), sensing (S), intuitive (I), thinking (T), feeling (F), judging (J), perceiving (P).

The use of general attitudes and personality traits combined enables the determination of typical characteristics and individual behavior and the content of that behavior.

III. METHODS AND ANALYSIS

A. Data collection and description

The original questionnaire was created and tested for previous research and offered online for completion from March 2013 to May 2015. In that period, 244 completely filled-in questionnaires were collected for the Croatia area. The same questionnaire was distributed to first-year students in the 2017/2018 academic year in Pula (Croatia) when additional 89 responses were collected. Given that it is a convenience sample, conclusions must not be generalized, but they can be used to gain insight into the situation.

The responses to questions about personality traits and general attitudes are compiled, and the respondents' age was corrected based on the year when respondents filled in the questionnaire. Collected data is classified according to age groups.

TABLE III
RELATIVE FREQUENCIES OF PERSONALITY TRAITS AND GENERAL ATTITUDES FOR EACH AGE GROUP

Age group	Number of respondents	Respondents age	I-E	N-S	F-T	P-J	T	I	A	Tr	S	E
(1) 1996 – 2000	97	18 - 22	0.5585	0.4988	0.4703	0.6070	0.6334	0.7339	0.7139	0.5419	0.4942	0.4942
(2) 1980 - 1995	201	23 - 38	0.5534	0.4624	0.4519	0.6333	0.6390	0.8246	0.6502	0.5361	0.5728	0.5155
(3) 1960 - 1979	35	38 - 58	0.5392	0.4538	0.4529	0.6281	0.6340	0.8317	0.6392	0.5348	0.5929	0.5034

Source: Author's calculation.

Table III describes general attitude and personality traits for each age group expressed as the mean of the relative frequencies. In continuation, age groups will be referred to as the first, second, and third age groups for respondents born in periods 1996 – 2000, 1980 – 1995, and 1960 – 1979, respectively.

The most frequent personality type is ENFJ. The comparison of average expression of each age group's traits and general attitudes reveals that the extraversion is slightly more expressed for the first age group, while the judging trait is expressed less. Regarding the general attitudes, it can be noticed that individualistic, social, and economical general attitudes are expressed less for the first age group, while the aesthetical general attitude is expressed more than for the other two groups. The hierarchy of the general attitudes for the first age group is

IATTrSE (Individual, Aesthetic, Theoretical, Traditional, Social and Economic), while hierarchy for the second and third age group is: IATSTrE (Individual, Aesthetical, Theoretical, Social, Traditional, Economical). Stated points out to change in frequencies of the general attitudes and consequently change in the hierarchy of the general attitudes at respondents of the first group compared to other two groups. In order to examine the statistical significance of the changes, observed deviations have to be tested.

B. Data analysis

One-way analysis of variance will be applied to determine statistically significant differences among the personality traits and general attitudes given the three age groups. Observed data were measured at an interval scale and recorded as a continuous variable. The data is classified according to the three age groups. The observations are mutually independent (the responses of one respondent do not influence the responses of other respondents). In order to achieve no outlier assumption, answers of five respondents are removed from further analysis. Given that each group has a different number of observations, a homogeneity of variances assumption must be confirmed. Based on Levene test, the hypothesis that the variances of personality traits and general attitudes given the age groups are equal is not rejected at 5% statistical significance level. Based on the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test, at the 5% statistical significance, the hypothesis about normal distribution can be rejected for most of the variables. Distributions' skewness, and kurtosis, show relatively small deviation from the normal distribution. As all of the other assumptions are met, the one-way analysis of variance will be applied to the data, following with additional confirmation with non-parametric Kruskal-Wallis test (one-way ANOVA on ranks), which is not sensitive to distribution normality, with the satisfied assumption of similarly shaped distributions.

General expression for analysis of variance of personality traits for three observed age groups is:

$$H_0 \dots \mu_{t1}^2 = \mu_{t2}^2 = \mu_{t3}^2$$

$$H_1 \dots \mu_{t1}^2 \neq \mu_{t2}^2 \neq \mu_{t3}^2,$$

where t denotes a trait, $t = \{IE, NS, FT, PJ\}$ and the index number denotes age group.

Research null- hypotheses are:

H_1 : there is no statistically significant difference between variations in extraversion-introversion traits among observed age groups

H_2 : there is no statistically significant difference between variations in sensing-intuitive traits among observed age groups

H_3 : there is no statistically significant difference between variations in thinking-feeling traits among observed age groups

H_4 : there is no statistically significant difference between variations in judging-perceiving traits among observed age groups.

General expression for analysis of variance of general attitudes for the three observed age groups is:

$$H_0 \dots \mu_{a1}^2 = \mu_{a2}^2 = \mu_{a3}^2$$

$$H_1 \dots \mu_{a1}^2 \neq \mu_{a2}^2 \neq \mu_{a3}^2,$$

where a denotes general attitude $a = \{T, I, Es, Tr, S, E\}$, and the index number denotes age group.

From the stated, research hypotheses follow:

H_5 : there is no statistically significant difference between variations in theoretical general attitude among observed age groups

H_6 : there is no statistically significant difference between variations in individualistic general attitude among observed age groups

H_7 : there is no statistically significant difference between variations in aesthetical general attitude among observed age groups

H_8 : there is no statistically significant difference between variations in traditional general attitude among observed age groups

H_9 : there is no statistically significant difference between variations in social general attitude among observed age groups

H_{10} : there is no statistically significant difference between variations in economic general attitude among observed age groups.

According to the hypotheses, a test is applied, and the results are presented in the Table 4.

TABLE IV
ONE-WAY ANALYSIS OF VARIANCE OF PERSONALITY TRAITS AND GENERAL ATTITUDES GIVEN THE AGE GROUPS

ANOVA		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Introversion – Extraversion personality trait	Between Groups	.193	2	.097	1.955	.143
	Within Groups	16.119	326	.049		
	Total	16.313	328			
Intuitive – Sensing Personality trait	Between Groups	.064	2	.032	1.513	.222
	Within Groups	6.942	326	.021		
	Total	7.006	328			
Feeling – Thinking Personality trait	Between Groups	.038	2	.019	.667	.514
	Within Groups	9.207	326	.028		
	Total	9.245	328			
Perceive – Judging Personality trait	Between Groups	.042	2	.021	1.063	.347
	Within Groups	6.469	326	.020		
	Total	6.512	328			
Theoretical General Attitude	Between Groups	.038	2	.019	.817	.443
	Within Groups	7.646	326	.023		
	Total	7.684	328			
Individual General Attitude	Between Groups	.440	2	.220	13.331	.000***
	Within Groups	5.383	326	.017		
	Total	5.824	328			
Aesthetical General Attitude	Between Groups	.410	2	.205	8.101	.000***
	Within Groups	8.255	326	.025		
	Total	8.666	328			
Traditional General Attitude	Between Groups	.071	2	.036	2.415	.091*
	Within Groups	4.796	326	.015		
	Total	4.867	328			
Social General Attitude	Between Groups	.321	2	.160	6.538	.002***
	Within Groups	7.996	326	.025		
	Total	8.317	328			

IV. RESULTS

Economic General Attitude	Between Groups	.009	2	.005	.212	.809
	Within Groups	7.132	326	.022		
	Total	7.141	328			

Note: Statistical significance denoted with *,** and ***; for 10%, 5% and 1% statistical significance, respectively.

Source: Author's calculation using SPSS.

Additionally, the Welch test is applied, pointing out statistically significant differences in individual, aesthetical and social attitude at 5% statistical significance. The Tahmane post-hoc test was applied to reveal more detailed differences. Tahmane test showed that at 5% statistical significance, there are differences in averages of individualistic and aesthetic attitudes which derive from the differences of the first and second, and first and third group, as well as the differences in average social attitude which derive from the differences between the first and second age group.

TABLE V
RESULT OF KRUSKAL-WALLIS TEST APPLIED TO DISTRIBUTIONS OF PERSONALITY TRAITS AND GENERAL ATTITUDES GIVEN THE AGE GROUPS

Null Hypothesis	Test	Sig
The distribution of Extraversion-Introversion trait is the same across categories of Age group	Independent samples Kruskal-Wallis Test	0.17
The distribution of Sensing-Intuitive trait is the same across categories of Age group	Independent samples Kruskal-Wallis Test	0.234
The distribution of Thinking-Feeling trait is the same across categories of Age group	Independent samples Kruskal-Wallis Test	0.518
The distribution of Judging-Perceiving trait is the same across categories of Age group	Independent samples Kruskal-Wallis Test	0.464
The distribution of Theoretical general attitude is the same across categories of Age group	Independent samples Kruskal-Wallis Test	0.59
The distribution of Individualistic general attitude is the same across categories of Age group	Independent samples Kruskal-Wallis Test	0.000***
The distribution of Aesthetical general attitude is the same across categories of Age group	Independent samples Kruskal-Wallis Test	0.000***
The distribution of Traditional general attitude is the same across categories of Age group	Independent samples Kruskal-Wallis Test	0.095*
The distribution of Social general attitude is the same across categories of Age group	Independent samples Kruskal-Wallis Test	0.002***
The distribution of Economical general attitude is the same across categories of Age group	Independent samples Kruskal-Wallis Test	0.674

Source: author's calculation using SPSS.

In order to determine if the personality traits and general attitudes of the respondents differ given the age groups, collected data is tested to reveal the source of the data variability over the age groups. Based on the applied test and the results (One-way analysis of variance, Welch test, Tahmane post-hoc test, and Kruskal-Wallis test), the following conclusions are made for the observed sample:

H_1 : the extraversion-introversion traits variations and the means among observed age groups are equal. The analysis points out that null-hypothesis is not rejected at the 5% statistical significance level null-hypothesis is not rejected. The conclusion is that there are no statistically significant differences in variations of an extraversion-introversion trait over the age groups.

H_2 : the sensing-intuitive traits variations and the means among observed age groups are equal. The analysis points out that null-hypothesis is not rejected at the 5% statistical significance level null-hypothesis is not rejected. The conclusion is that there are no statistically significant differences in variations of a sensing-intuitive trait over the age groups.

H_3 : the thinking-feeling traits variations and the means among observed age groups are equal. The analysis points out that null-hypothesis is not rejected at the 5% statistical significance level null-hypothesis is not rejected. The conclusion is that there are no statistically significant differences in variations of a thinking-feeling trait over the age groups.

H_4 : the judging-perceiving traits variations and the means among observed age groups are equal. The analysis points out that null-hypothesis is not rejected at the 5% statistical significance level null-hypothesis is not rejected, and the conclusion is that there are no statistically significant differences in variations of a judging-perceiving trait over the age groups.

H_5 : the theoretical general attitude variations and the means among observed age groups are equal. The analysis points out that null-hypothesis is not rejected at the 5% statistical significance level null-hypothesis is not rejected, and the conclusion is that there are no statistically significant differences in variations of a theoretical general attitude over the age groups.

H_6 : the individualistic general attitude variations and the means among observed age groups are not equal. The analysis points out that at the 5% statistical significance level null-hypothesis is rejected, and the conclusion is that there are statistically significant differences in variations of an individualistic general attitude over the age groups. The interpretation of the result can be extended with Tamhane's post-hoc test and insights from Table III, which point out that the change in the frequencies of the individualistic general attitude occurs in the first age group, which is less expressed for this age group than in other two age groups.

H_7 : the aesthetical general attitude variations and the means among observed age groups are not equal. Analysis points put that at the 5% statistical significance level null-hypothesis is rejected and the conclusion is that there are statistically

significant differences in variations of aesthetical general attitude over the age groups. The interpretation of the result can be extended with Tamhane's post-hoc test and insights from Table III, which indicate that the difference arises from the change in aesthetical general attitude in the first age group.

H_8 : the traditional general attitude variations among observed age groups are equal. The analysis points out that null-hypothesis is not rejected at the 5% statistical significance level null-hypothesis is not rejected. The conclusion is that there are no statistically significant differences in variations of traditional general attitude over the age groups.

H_9 : the social general attitude variations among observed age groups are not equal. The analysis points out that null-hypothesis is rejected at the 5% statistical significance level, and the conclusion is that there are statistically significant differences in variations of the social general attitude over the age groups. The Tamhane's post-hoc test and Table III point out that the social general attitude is less expressed at the first age group than in other age groups.

H_{10} the economic general attitude variations among observed age groups are equal. The analysis points out that null-hypothesis is not rejected at the 5% statistical significance level null-hypothesis is not rejected, and the conclusion is that there are no statistically significant differences in variations of the economic general attitude over the age groups.

V. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

In analyses of psychological and sociological characteristics of a particular age group or generation, usually, the emphasis is on a determination of specificities and differences. Those insights are used in market segmentation and strategies, labor market analysis, and the field of human resources. This paper focuses on questioning relatively permanent psychological constructs: personality traits and general attitudes and their comparison over the age groups.

The results indicate no statistically significant differences among respondents' personality traits' variations, given the different age groups. The findings indicate that no statistically significant change can be noted for the behavioral patterns of respondents from the first age group (1996 – 2000) concerning the other two age groups.

However, the results show some statistically significant differences in the behavior content between the groups, precisely the noted differences in individualistic, aesthetical, and social general attitudes. In addition, the change in average frequencies of the general attitudes points out to a change in the general attitudes' hierarchy. Most of the observed data variations derive from the differences in the first age group in relation to the other two groups. However, it is interesting to notice that no statistically significant differences arise from the variations between the second and the third groups.

Given the observed changes in general individualistic attitude at respondents of the first age group, their content of the activities will be less inclined to gain power and influence, aspire to status, control, stand out, gain responsibility, and achieve uniqueness and distinctiveness. That might indicate

that respondents from this group will be, on average, less ambitious, less standing-out, and less inclined to gain responsibility, which can be used as a reference while employing members from this group and the additional cue for human resources for a re-creation of motivation measures, as well as adjustment of the work demands. In addition, for most of the observed members of this group, it is unlikely that they will engage in entrepreneurial endeavors. The possible implications of this general attitude for purchase behavior indicate, for example, that companies might want to step back from the status and prestige in their promotional messages if they want to engage members of this group into purchase behavior. Ozkan and Solmaz (2015b) compare generations Y and Z, where the first one prefers autonomy in work, while the latter seeks to validate their ideas and listen to their ideas. The stated remark is in line with the observed decrease in individualistic general attitude frequency. Krsulja et al. (2015) specify overconfidence in own knowledge as a characteristic of the generation Z, which is not in line with the findings regarding the decrease of the individual general attitude at individuals born between 1996 and 2000 in this research. However, Ilišin and Gvozdanović (2016) state that individual autonomy as a value rises with the rise of the social competencies in youth. Based on the stated and the fact that it requires time to gain social competencies, it can be concluded that increasing the respondent's individualistic attitude intensity is possible in the future.

Based on the general aesthetical attitude changes, respondents born in the period 1996 – 2000 will strive for harmony, beauty, comfort, tolerance, balance, enjoying the moment, self-fulfillment, and subjective understanding of the experiences more than the other two age groups. Stated is in line with the search for the lost identity, which Krsulja et al. (2015) state as one of the characteristics of the generation Z. Ozkan and Solmaz's (2015b) characteristic of the generation Z – self-perception as unrealistic/ dreamer, can be related to this general attitude. The implications of this general attitude can be observed through employment and purchase behavior. As members of this group (respondents) value comfort, tolerance, etc., employers should strive to create a harmonic company climate and use experiences and comfort as guidelines for creating motivational policy. As an age group with this general attitude more expressed than the previous two, experiencing the world through their own experiences will likely incline them to travel more and try out more novelties in each segment of their lives compared to members of the other two groups. Wells et al. (2018) stated that generation Z seeks purpose, and the results of this analysis for the members of the same age group confirm that. The authors also state that this characteristic led to an increase in the purpose statements in promotional messages, which seems to be an appropriate strategy. The respondents' strive for beauty, tolerance, and enjoyment in the moment also presents a possibility for a marketing approach.

The determined variations in the general social attitude are statistically significant and derive mainly from the frequency distribution of the respondents from the first age group and the smaller average of that attitude. That means that the

respondents from the first group will, on average, demonstrate less orientation to others, altruism, empathy, and action to improve society. That might indicate that they will be less inclined to teamwork, social activities, and joint actions than the previous two age groups. From the business perspective, if they employ a respondent from the first group, they might need to adjust the work setting to allow more individual work and decrease gatherings and social activities. The finding is accordant with Karakas et al.'s (2015) finding of the lack of social engagements of the members of new generations. The characteristics such as loyalty, agreeing with others, reconcilability, helping others, and willingness to work in a group were examined by Ozkan and Solmaz (2015b). They determined moderate to high self-assessment of those characteristics at their respondents, contrary to the decrease of the average social attitude in this research. However, high estimates from Ozkan and Solmaz's (2015b) research can be explained by using the self-assessment technique.

The stated changes in general attitudes also manifest in the hierarchy of the average frequencies, following the rotation of social and traditional attitudes at fourth and fifth place. The traditional general attitude, which gained a fourth place, denotes obeying the rules, system, hierarchy, established patterns, order, structure, principles, and aspiration to systematicity and routine.

The average frequencies of social and economic general attitudes are equal for the first age group. Despite the minor changes in the average frequencies, the first three attitudes did not change a position and remained, respectively: individualistic, aesthetical, and theoretical general attitudes. As analysis did not point out any statistically significant difference for the economic attitude among the age groups (in contrast to the difference in the general social attitude), the general economic attitude is given the last place, the same as with the other two age groups. That means that the respondents find that decision-making based on benefit and profit, the valuation of the environment and themselves based on economic and material indicators, and aspiration to practical solutions and applications are the least important.

It is also interesting to notice the slight deviations in the personality traits and general attitudes of the respondents born from 1996 to 2000 compared to respondents born in the period from 1980 to 1995. The observation leads to the conclusion that a more detailed examination of the similarities and differences of those two age groups is required, just as a reexamination of a reference framework for defining age groups in Croatia (as most of the proposed time references for age groups definitions is taken from the foreign authors). Despite globalization processes, different socio-economical environments from each country can influence the specific set of experiences in individuals' formation periods, thus influencing a set of characteristics that define each generation (besides the age groups).

General attitudes and personality traits have theoretical and practical applications in employee analysis in human resources and internal marketing and negotiation analysis, and purchase behavior. Even though the noted changes have to be confirmed

with extensive research on a representative sample, experts and scientists can use stated results as insights during adjustment of the motivation and delegation system and promotion and sales approach to persons born in the period 1996 – 2000 in Croatia. Those individuals become of age, they are starting to make decisions on their own, engaged (or soon will engage) into the labor market, which will increase their purchase power, and their share in the population (and market) will continue to grow. Based on the discussion, it can be concluded that, even though specific differences were proved between the age groups, those differences are relatively small in overall behavior. They relate to the changes in individualistic, aesthetical, and social general attitudes (of the ten observed characteristics). The results also show more similarities than differences among the age groups considering the relatively permanent psychological constructs. That leads to further consideration of the possibility that most of the differences arise from environmental influences and not essential psychological differences, which deserves necessary attention and examination in future research. Besides that, the revealed differences may arise from the difference in the age, and there is a possibility that those differences diminish with maturing of the respondents of the last age group (as the results show no statistically significant differences between second and third group), which should also be examined in future research.

Given the fast technological changes and continually changing environment that result in different life experiences while overcoming the differences, it might be helpful to emphasize discovered similarities.

The research limitation derives from using the small convenience sample from Croatia, which disables generalization of conclusions. The results may serve only as an insight into similarities and differences in general attitudes and personality traits among the observed age groups. Stated leads to recommendation for future generalization of the findings, and detailed examination of the similarities and differences of personality traits and general attitudes, not just between age groups, but to extend the research to the generations.

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